

TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING HEALTHY LIFESTYLE SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7838004>

Abstract. *This article highlights innovative and complex technologies for the formation of students' healthy lifestyle skills in the context of education and training. The concept of a healthy lifestyle is widely understood among the population, and it is important that this concept is based on the content of biological education.*

Keywords: *vitagen, didactic, constructive factors, healthcare technology, sanogenic technologies.*

Today, young people, especially schoolchildren, need a pedagogical and psychological approach to such issues as acquiring healthy lifestyle skills, maintaining the health of themselves and others. The creation of an unhealthy environment for the majority of students in a general education school, the inability to acquire knowledge in existing subjects, various disagreements between peers or in the family make children susceptible to emotions. As a result, children experience fear, phobia, violence or selfishness. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of developing healthy lifestyle skills among students, as well as the effective use of HRT (healthy lifestyle) technologies in the content of biological sciences. Our teachers carried out research work on the formation of healthy lifestyle skills among young people, in which this concept was explained in the context of most hygiene factors. In particular, in the studies of the teacher D.Zh. Sharipova highlights the problems of organizing a healthy lifestyle of students on the basis of hygienic education, and special attention is paid to revealing the essence of research on the organization of hygienic education, as well as developing the content of the experience of organizing hygienic education in the form of an integral system. [1]. After all, this approach creates the basis for the formation of a clear idea of the nature of the research work. The scientist-teacher M.M.Isabayeva in the content of her research work explained the methodological system for the formation of healthy lifestyle skills among students of biological education and described it in the content of biological education. A healthy lifestyle is a combination of factors that positively affect the morphological, anatomical, physiological processes occurring in the body from the period of embryonic development to age periods, and is the basis of mental, spiritual and physical health. of a person, preserving the health of himself and those around him, and consciously organizing his way of life, is a complex of sharing knowledge, skills and abilities [2].

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature showed that the promotion of public health, scientific approaches that develop sanogenic thinking based on our national values, customs and traditions, pedagogical conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the process of out-of-school education and training, cooperation of public organizations in the formation of a healthy lifestyle among youth. A number of research works have been carried out in the microdistrict on the pedagogical foundations of preparing girls for a family based on a healthy lifestyle, the development of an environmental and hygienic culture in the formation of a healthy lifestyle. Pupils on guard of their own and others' health, health and knowledge of the factors that threaten the continuity of life, that is, protection from addictive behavior, allows you

to develop immunity to fight aggressive forces. It consists in the development of sanogenic thinking by focusing on spiritual masterpieces, wise words and stories in order to ensure the mental and emotional maturity of students. The national orientation of the process of forming students' healthy lifestyle skills requires, when choosing the content of this process, attention to universal and national values spiritual masterpieces, hadiths, wise words and stories. In the process of developing healthy lifestyle skills, an integral connection between training and education is necessary to expand the scientific outlook of students, to form a comprehensively mature personality with an active social position. This means that it will be covered based on didactic factors. Vitagen is information (based on life experience) selected by the teacher in accordance with the didactic goals of the new subject and is considered a teaching material intended for use in the process of studying the subject [3]. The Vitagen learning material has been selected to create healthy lifestyle content that is the foundation of the Vitagen student experience and must meet the requirements of the subject's behavior patterns. The didactic factor is the vital information that the teacher communicates to students in the context of the content of education, means and methods of teaching. Based on these factors, in the process of biological education, it is advisable to use the following innovative technologies related to the formation of a healthy lifestyle among students.

Health education means the formation of practical skills through the use of theoretical concepts aimed at maintaining the biological health of the body. Health care skills are formed by organizing a "health minute" at biology lessons, teaching how to perform practical educational tasks in the "Health Corner" after school hours (providing first aid for bone fractures and sprains, etc.). This process allows effective use of didactic tools: textbooks, teaching aids, scientific articles, medical journals, multimedia resources and medical information. Educational technologies that develop sanogenic thinking are aimed at correcting behavior that is contrary to the rules of etiquette, protecting students from addictive behavior, organizing spiritual and educational activities related to a healthy lifestyle, healthy sports, allowing you to apply the knowledge gained. about a healthy lifestyle in the course of their life. teaches you to take care of your own health and that of others.

These technologies are inextricably linked and are recommended for use in all forms of biology education.

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